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Green Chemistry in Action: Designing a Plant-Based Hydrogel Using Red Banana (*Musa acuminata*)

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Abstract: Natural plant-based materials are increasingly being explored as alternatives to synthetic ingredients in the formulation of hydrogels, especially for use in topical and biomedical applications. This study focuses on the preparation and evaluation of a hydrogel using *Musa acuminata* (Red Banana) extract, known for its antioxidant and medicinal properties. The extract was obtained through a water-ethanol extraction process and incorporated into a Carbopol-based hydrogel. Phytochemical analysis showed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and saponins. The formulated hydrogel was then evaluated for key parameters such as pH (7.00 ± 0.16), viscosity (4500 ± 73 cP), appearance, odor, and washability. The hydrogel showed good physical characteristics, a smooth reddish-brown texture, and was easy to wash off without leaving residue. Overall, the results suggest that red banana extract can be effectively used in hydrogel formulations and may offer a natural, skin-friendly alternative for topical applications.

Key Words: Red Banana, Hydrogel, Phytochemical Screening

1. Introduction

The most significant source of medicinal medications and a key factor in the survival of ethnic and tribal societies are plants. According to WHO, for millions of people in the rural areas of developing countries, which is about 80% of the world's population, herbal medicines serve the health requirements [1]. In recent years, natural plant-based materials have gained increasing attention in the development of biocompatible hydrogels, particularly for applications in wound care, drug delivery, and tissue engineering. Among these, Red Dacca, scientifically known as *Musa acuminata* and commonly referred to as Red Banana, is a unique variety grown in tropical and subtropical regions, including Southeast Asia, India (notably Tamil Nadu, Kerala, and Karnataka), Australia, and parts of Central and South America. In India, it is especially prized in Tamil Nadu and Kerala, with commercial cultivation concentrated in Kanyakumari and Tirunelveli. Known locally as Chandra Bale in Karnataka and LalVel chi in Bihar, this variety stands out for its thick, smooth peel and vibrant coloration, ranging from reddish-purple to deep

Fig 1: *Musa acuminata*

maroon depending on its antioxidant content. The fruit is shorter and plumper than the Cavendish type (measuring 10–18 cm in length and 3–5 cm in diameter), making it more resistant to bruising. It offers a sweet taste with a hint of raspberry, a pleasant aroma, and a slightly greasy texture due to the presence of alkaloids [2, 3]

Cultivated red bananas are either seedless or contain tiny, undeveloped seeds and are often propagated through tissue culture. Wild types, however, have large, hard black seeds that make them difficult to eat. Compared to Cavendish bananas, red bananas require more specific growing conditions, including high humidity, consistent warm temperatures (24–29°C or 75–85°F), and protection from strong winds, as their leaves are more fragile. The growth cycle takes about 9 to 12 months. However, cultivation is challenged by high susceptibility to diseases such as Panama disease, black leaf streak, banana bunchy top virus, and Fusarium wilt, which can severely affect yield and plant health [4, 5]

Hydrogels derived from plant extracts present a natural and potentially biocompatible option for a wide range of applications, especially in wound healing. These materials can be engineered to replicate the characteristics of natural tissue, offer efficient transport properties, and enable the controlled release of bioactive compounds found in the plant sources [6]. This research aims to evaluate the potential of Red Banana-derived hydrogel as a natural, sustainable, and functional biomaterial. The study focuses on extracting bioactive compounds from the fruit and assessing the hydrogel's physicochemical properties. Red banana-based hydrogels may offer an eco-friendly and cost-effective alternative to synthetic materials currently used in medical treatments.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1 Materials

The fruits of *Musa acuminata* were identified and collected in the month of March from the Namsai district of Arunachal Pradesh. Water used for all the experimental purposes is double-distilled. All the chemicals were of laboratory grade and used without further processing.

2.2 Extraction of *Musa acuminata* fruits

Fresh fruits of *Musa acuminata* were collected and washed under running water to remove foreign substances. It was then peeled, cut into small pieces to let it dry faster and later let it

dry under normal temperature. It took 3-4 days to dry completely. the dried peel was grinded perfectly into fine powder. the coarsely fine powdered which is the menstruum is added with distilled water and ethanol in a volumetric flask. It is then closed and stirred periodically in an incubator shaker for about 48 hours to ensure complete extraction. The micelle is separated by filtration using filter paper. Soon after that, the micelle is separated from menstruum by evaporation in the water bath until we get the extract. The extracts were then transferred to an airtight container and kept in the refrigerator at 4°C for further analysis [7].

2.3 Phytochemical screening of *Musa acuminata* fruits extract

The preliminary phytochemical evaluation was performed by using standard methods.

2.3.1 Detection of alkaloids

Mayer's test: In 2 ml of extract solution, few drops of Mayer's reagent was added.

2.3.2 Detection of Flavonoids

Alkaline reagent test: In the 2ml extract, 2ml of NaOH was added.

2.3.3 Detection of tannins:

Ferric chloride test: Take 2ml extract with few drops of FeCl₃.

2.3.4 Detection of saponins:

Foam test: Shake 2ml extract with 5ml distilled water.

2.3.5 Detection of phenols:

Ferric chloride test: Take 2ml extract and add few drops of FeCl₃.

2.3.6 Detection of terpenoids:

Salkowski test: Add 2ml extract with 2ml chloroform, then carefully add H₂SO₄.

2.3.7 Detection of glycosides:

Keller-Kiliani test: Add 2ml extract with 1ml glacial acetic acid, then add FeCl₃ and lastly conc.H₂SO₄.

2.3.8 Detection of carbohydrates:

Benedict's test: Add 2ml extract with 2ml benedict's reagent, then heat in water bath.

Iodine test: Take 2ml extract then few drops of iodine solution.

2.3.9 Detection of proteins:

Biuret test: Add 2ml extract with 2ml NaOH then few drops of CuSO_4 .

2.3.10 Detection of lipids:

Sudan III test: Add 2ml extract then few drops of Sudan III reagent, then shake.

Grease spot test: Rub the extract on filter paper and let it dry [8].

2.4 Preparation of Red Banana-Based Hydrogel

To formulate the hydrogel, 1 g of Carbopol was dispersed in 50 mL of distilled water and stirred using a magnetic stirrer on a hot plate until a clear gel-like consistency was achieved. Once the base gel formed, methyl paraben sodium was added to the mixture as a preservative and stirred continuously until it was completely dissolved. Following this, an additional 50 mL of distilled water was incorporated into the formulation to adjust the volume. Subsequently, 10 mL of propylene glycol was added to act as a humectant, enhancing the moisture-retention properties of the gel. After allowing the mixture to blend uniformly, 5 mL of ethanol and 1 g of red banana extract were introduced to the formulation. Finally, a few drops of triethanolamine were added to adjust the pH and complete the hydrogel preparation, resulting in a smooth and stable red banana-based hydrogel [9].

2.5 Evaluation of Hydrogel Formulation

To assess the quality and functional properties of the red banana-based hydrogel, the following evaluation parameters were conducted:

2.5.1 Microscopic Characteristics

The hydrogel formulation was visually and physically examined to assess its texture, color, and odor. These characteristics were evaluated to ensure uniformity, aesthetic acceptability, and absence of phase separation or particulate matter [7, 13].

2.5.2 pH Determination

The pH of the hydrogel was measured using a digital pH meter to ensure compatibility with skin. For this, 2 grams of the extract-loaded hydrogel were dispersed in distilled water and stirred to obtain a homogeneous suspension. The total volume was then adjusted to 40 mL, and the pH of the solution was recorded [10].

2.5.3 Viscosity Measurement

The viscosity of the hydrogel was evaluated using a Brookfield viscometer to determine its flow properties and consistency. This test helps assess the hydrogel's spreadability and ease of application on the skin [11].

2.5.4 Washability Test

The washability of the hydrogel was assessed by applying a small amount of the formulation to the skin or a smooth surface and then rinsing it under running water. The ease with which the hydrogel could be removed indicated its washability, an important parameter for user comfort and product acceptance [12].

3. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data obtained from the average of three readings were analysed statistically using GraphPad Prism 8.0.2 software (GraphPad Inc. San Diego, CA, USA). All the data shown in tables and figures are mean \pm standard deviation and were obtained by performing the tests in triplicate.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Phytochemical screening

The red banana (*Musa acuminata*) extract was subjected to qualitative phytochemical screening to identify the presence of various bioactive compounds. The results indicated positive responses for all tested phytoconstituents, suggesting the extract contains a diverse range of bioactive molecules such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenols, terpenoids, glycosides, carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids. These findings support the potential therapeutic and functional properties of the red banana extract, particularly in applications like hydrogel formulation for wound healing.

Fig 2: Results of phytochemical screening

S.No.	Phytochemical	Test Performed	Observation	Result
1	Alkaloids	Mayer's Test	Creamy white precipitate	Positive
2	Flavonoids	Alkaline Reagent Test	Intense yellow color	Positive
3	Tannins	Ferric Chloride Test	Blue-black or greenish-black coloration	Positive
4	Saponins	Foam Test	Persistent froth	Positive
5	Phenols	Ferric Chloride Test	Deep blue/black coloration	Positive
6	Terpenoids	Salkowski Test	Reddish-brown interface	Positive
7	Glycosides	Keller-Kiliani Test	Reddish-brown ring at interface	Positive
8	Carbohydrates	Benedict's and Iodine Test	Brick-red precipitate, blue-black color	Positive
9	Proteins	Biuret Test	Violet/purple color	Positive
10	Lipids	Sudan III & Grease Spot Test	Red-stained layer, translucent grease spot	Positive

4.2 Formulation of Red Banana-Based Hydrogel

The hydrogel formulation was prepared by first dispersing 1 g of Carbopol in 50 mL of distilled water with continuous stirring using a magnetic stirrer on a hot plate until a clear gel base was formed. To this gel, methyl paraben sodium was added as a preservative and stirred until fully dissolved. The volume was then adjusted by adding an additional 50 mL of distilled water. Next, 10 mL of propylene glycol was incorporated to act as a humectant, enhancing the moisture-retention properties of the hydrogel. After thorough mixing, 5 mL of ethanol and 1 g of red banana extract were added to the formulation. Finally, a few drops of triethanolamine were introduced to neutralize the pH and stabilize the gel, resulting in a smooth, homogeneous red banana-based hydrogel suitable for further evaluation.

Fig 3: Preparation of Hydrogel

4.3 Evaluation of Red Banana-Based Hydrogel

4.3.1 Microscopic Characteristics

The hydrogel formulation was visually and physically examined to assess its texture, color, and odor. These characteristics were evaluated to ensure uniformity, aesthetic acceptability, and the absence of phase separation or particulate matter. The hydrogel exhibited a smooth texture and a consistent reddish-brown color. The odor was characteristic of the banana extract used, confirming the presence of the active ingredient without any off-smells. Compared to an ideal hydrogel, which should present a

homogeneous and stable appearance with a pleasant or neutral odor, the formulation met these criteria, indicating good physical stability and user acceptability.

4.3.2 pH Determination

The pH of the hydrogel was measured using a digital pH meter to confirm its compatibility with the skin. Two grams of the extract-loaded hydrogel were dispersed in distilled water, stirred thoroughly to form a homogeneous suspension, and the volume was adjusted to 40 mL prior to pH measurement. The recorded pH was 7.00 ± 0.16 , which is within the acceptable range for topical formulations (typically between 5.5 and 7.5) to minimize skin irritation and maintain skin barrier integrity. Thus, the hydrogel's pH closely aligns with the ideal pH range for skin compatibility.

Fig 4: Determination of pH

4.3.3 Viscosity Measurement

Viscosity was assessed using a Brookfield viscometer to determine the hydrogel's flow properties and consistency, critical for ensuring ease of application and appropriate spreadability on the skin. The hydrogel showed a viscosity of 4500 ± 73 cP, indicating a moderately thick formulation that is neither too runny nor too stiff. Ideal hydrogels typically exhibit viscosity values that allow smooth spreading without dripping, generally ranging between 1000 to 10,000 cP depending on the intended use. Therefore, the measured viscosity suggests the formulation has suitable rheological properties for topical application.

4.3.4 Washability

The washability of the hydrogel was assessed by applying a small amount of the formulation to the skin or a smooth surface, followed by rinsing under running water. The ease with which the hydrogel was removed served as an indicator of its washability, an important parameter for user comfort, ease of use, and overall product acceptance.

The hydrogel was found to be easily washable, with no sticky residue left behind. Compared to an ideal hydrogel, which should be non-greasy and removable with minimal rinsing, the tested formulation met the expected criteria. This confirms its suitability for topical application and enhances its potential for consumer acceptability.

5. Conclusion

The present study demonstrates the potential of *Musa acuminata* (Red Banana) extract as a valuable natural ingredient in hydrogel formulation. The successful extraction of phytochemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, and saponins indicates the presence of compounds with possible therapeutic effects. The formulated hydrogel showed favorable physicochemical properties, including a neutral pH suitable for skin application, good viscosity for spreadability, smooth texture, characteristic odor, and excellent washability. These results suggest that red banana-based hydrogels can serve as a promising, eco-friendly alternative to conventional synthetic products used in topical treatments. Further research, including antimicrobial testing and *in vivo* studies, is recommended to validate its effectiveness in wound healing and other dermatological applications.

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